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Review Study

Phytochemistry, Pharmacology, and Therapeutic Applications of *Viola odorata*: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

Viola odorata, sometimes called English violet or sweet violet, is a herbaceous perennial plant that belongs to the *Violaceae* family. It has long been used for its medicinal properties in a variety of traditional medical systems, such as Persian, Ayurvedic, and Unani medicine. The plant, which has a rich phytochemical profile that includes flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, and phenolic compounds, is native to Europe and Asia. These components help to explain the plant's remarkable anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antibacterial, and antioxidant qualities. Research has shown that it is effective in treating a variety of illnesses, including asthma, diabetes, liver problems, cardiovascular disease, respiratory disorders, and sleeplessness. The plant's sedative, expectorant, diuretic, and hepatoprotective properties are also recognised. Research in the preclinical and clinical stages has validated its safety and efficacy at therapeutic dosages. The conservation and sustainable cultivation of *Viola odorata* are crucial due to its medicinal significance and economic potential in both traditional and modern phytotherapy.

INTRODUCTION

Viola odorata, often called the English violet or sweet violet, is a perennial herb, A species of the family *Violaceae*. The plant is native to Europe, Asia, and North Africa. It has been widely approved for its various medicinal properties and

applications in conventional medical systems like Ancient Persian Treatment and Ayurveda, and Unani medicine¹. Historically, it has been used for various ailments, from respiratory issues like coughs and colds to dermatological conditions and insomnia.²

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The pharmacological ability of *Viola odorata* can be attributed to its rich phytochemical profile, which includes flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds.³ These chemical constituents have been documented to exhibit significant antioxidant and antimicrobial activities, thus underpinning the traditional uses of the plant in treating infections and inflammatory conditions.⁴ For instance, studies have indicated that the antimicrobial efficacy of *Viola odorata* extracts is noteworthy, showing efficacy against various pathogenic bacteria related to respiratory infections and other ailments.^{5,6} A recent examination also highlighted the presence of cycloviolacins in the plant, which contribute to its antifungal properties.^{7,8} The plant's sedative effects have gained interest in the treatment of insomnia, with systematic reviews validating its efficacy in promoting sleep.^{9,10} In ancient medicinal texts, it has been lauded as an expectorant and antipyretic, indicating its multifaceted therapeutic applications.¹¹ Furthermore, the volatile compounds responsible for its distinct fragrance, such as nona-2,6-dienal, can also contribute to its calming effects on the nervous system.¹² The cultivation and conservation of *Viola odorata* are crucial, given its ecological significance and potential economic benefits derived from its medicinal and ornamental values. However, continuous research and sustainable practices are needed to ensure its availability and efficacy in traditional and contemporary medicine.¹³ A significant majority of the global population depends on herbal and traditional medicine as a primary form of healthcare.¹⁴ For centuries, medicinal plants and plant-based remedies have

been essential in managing health and treating diseases.¹⁵ Historical records from ancient civilisations—such as Mesopotamia, Indian Ayurveda, traditional Chinese medicine, and Greek Unani medicine—demonstrate the widespread use of herbs for healing various illnesses.^{16,17} Numerous plants are known to produce bioactive compounds, some of which contribute to distinct flavors or aromas, while others serve as antioxidants or antimicrobial agents.¹⁸ One such plant, *Viola odorata*, is popularly referred to as Sweet Violet, English Violet, Common Violet, florist's violet, or Garden Violet, which belongs to the family Violaceae.¹⁹ The sweet and unmistakable scent of this flower has been used in production of many cosmetic fragrances and perfumes.¹⁶ This herb is valued as an expectorant, diaphoretic, antipyretic, diuretic²⁰ and as a laxative in bilious affections. It is used alone or in mixture with other herbs for catarrhal, pulmonary troubles and for calculous affections. *Viola odorata* exhibits antimycotic, antibacterial, and antifungal properties, making it a potent remedy for conditions like eczema.²¹ This herb is widely recognized in various traditional medicine systems, including Iranian, Greco-Arab, Ayurvedic, and Unani, for treating respiratory ailments such as whooping cough, as well as neurological and inflammatory conditions like headaches, migraines, insomnia, sore throat, and epilepsy in both children and adults. It is commonly administered as a decoction, jam, or syrup for therapeutic purposes.²²

PHYTOCHEMICALS PRESENT IN *VIOLA ODORATA*

Table 1. Preliminary phytochemical analysis of leaf Ethanolic extracts of VIOLA ODORATA.

Phytoconstituents	Test	<i>Viola odorata</i> Extract
Flavonoids ²³	Lead acetate	+
	Shinoda test	+
Alkaloids ^{24,25}	Dragendroff's test	+
Phenols	Ferric Chloride test	-
Carbohydrates	Molisch's test	-
	Fehling test	-
	Benedict's Test	-
Saponins	Froth test	+
Glycosides ²⁶	Keller- Kilani test	+
	Antimony trichoride test	
Triterpenoids	Salkowski test	-
Tannins ²⁷	Lead acetate test	+
Steroids ²⁷	Salkowski test	+

Figure No. 1 Preliminary phytochemical analysis of leaf Ethanolic extracts of VIOLA ODORATA.

PLANT DESCRIPTION

Viola odorata (sweet violet) is a temperate-zone plant that is typically found in regions with mild climates. It is native to Europe and parts of Asia, but has since spread to many other areas due to cultivation. The typical height of *Viola odorata* ranges from 10 cm to 30 cm (approximately 4 to 12 inches). This can vary slightly depending on environmental conditions like soil quality and sunlight. The spread or width of the plant can reach around 20 cm to 30 cm (approximately 8 to 12 inches), as it forms low-growing, mat-like clusters.²⁸ The leaves of *Viola odorata* are heart-

shaped, with leaf blades usually around 3 cm to 6 cm (1.2 to 2.4 inches) in length.²⁹ The leaves are typically arranged in a rosette pattern close to the ground. The flowers are small, ranging in size from 2 cm to 3 cm (0.8 to 1.2 inches) across. The flowers are fragrant, with five petals, usually violet, purple, or white in color, depending on the cultivar. The plant grows from creeping rhizomes, which allows it to spread along the ground. This growth form can lead to dense patches of the plant over time.³⁰

HABITAT

Commonly referred to as the common violet or sweet violet, *Viola odorata* is a herbaceous perennial plant that is indigenous to areas of Asia and Europe. It usually grows best in areas that are damp and shaded. Deciduous forests are home to *Viola odorata*, which thrives in partial to full shade at the forest's border. Originally from Europe and Asia, sweet violet, or *Viola odorata*, has spread to various parts of the world through introduction and naturalization.³¹

TRADITIONAL USES

Viola odorata, widely recognized as sweet violet, possesses an extensive heritage in traditional medicine. It has a rich history of traditional uses in various medicinal practices. It is utilized for treating respiratory issues, headaches, coughs, and even emotional ailments, often valued for its expectorant and anti-inflammatory properties.³²

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIONS

Pharmacological research on medicinal plants involves a scientific evaluation of their therapeutic effects, potential health benefits, and possible adverse reactions. Such studies validate the plant's medicinal use and provide a foundation for developing new formulations and applications in healthcare.³²

Anti-inflammatory effect.

A clinical study evaluated the results of using a common purple (*Viola odorata*) oral infusion in combination with amoxiclav co- and fexofenadine to treat persistent tonsillitis and peritonsillar abscess. The findings revealed that regular use of the violet decoction significantly reduced the recurrence rates of both conditions. An aqueous extract of violet petals has been evaluated for the management of formalin-induced lung injury in rats.^{28,33} Pretreatment with the extract showed moderate effectiveness in preventing lung damages, which was found to be comparable to that of hydrocortisone.^{33,34}

Antihypertensive and antidiabetic activities

Preclinical studies using anesthetized rats and isolated cardiac tissues (atria and aorta) demonstrated that *Viola odorata* leaf extract effectively improved cardiovascular health. When administered to rats on an atherogenic diet, the extract:

- Reduced total cholesterol, LDL, and atherogenic index
- Increased HDL levels without altering triglycerides or glucose
- Exhibited antihypertensive and vasorelaxant effects
- Promoted weight loss

These findings confirm its potential in managing metabolic syndrome by addressing hypertension, dyslipidemia, and obesity.³⁵

Antioxidant activity

Research on *Viola odorata* leaf extracts identified valuable bioactive compounds, including polyphenols, flavonoids, and alkaloids. The study demonstrated notable antioxidant capacity through standardised assays, indicating potential therapeutic applications for oxidative stress management. The extracts showed high levels of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, and phenolics. They found that ethanolic extract showed the highest radical scavenging activity and ferric reducing potential. Advanced chromatographic techniques were employed to analyse *Viola odorata* extracts.³⁸

- HPLC quantification verified stigmasterol content
- TLC fingerprinting confirmed stigmasterol presence

Respiratory Activity

Mittal P *et.al* (2015) investigated the *Viola odorata* demonstrates significant medicinal value through its rich phytochemical profile, containing bioactive compounds like flavonoids, alkaloids, and saponins. Pharmacological studies confirm its:

- Antioxidant properties

- **Cardioprotective** effects (cholesterol modulation, antihypertensive action) not demonstrate any significant pain-relieving effects.⁴⁰
- **Antiinflammatory** and **antimicrobial** activities

These findings support its traditional uses and suggest potential applications in modern phytotherapy. It has traditionally been used to treat respiratory and inflammatory conditions. This review article is to cover the recent advancement in the pharmacological and phytochemical potential of the drug *Viola odorata*, which contains alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, methyl salicylate, mucilage, and vitamins.³⁹

Hepatoprotective activity

Muhammad A et.al (2014) evaluated the Aqueous methanolic extract of *Viola odorata*'s hepatoprotective properties against mice's liver damage caused by paracetamol. A study on *Viola odorata* (*V. odorata*) found that its aqueous methanolic extract (250 and 500 mg/kg) significantly reduced liver enzyme levels and total bilirubin in paracetamol-intoxicated mice. Histopathological analysis showed reduced inflammation and cell damage. Flavonoids like luteolin and isorhamnetin were identified, which may contribute to the liver-protective effects. The study concluded that *V. odorata* helps protect against paracetamol-induced liver damage in mice.

Analgesic activity

Kannappan N et.al (2011) A study assessed the pain-relieving effects of *Viola odorata* aerial parts using different solvent extracts (n-hexane, butanolic, methanolic, and aqueous) in rat models. The results indicated that the aqueous and methanolic extracts exhibited notable analgesic activity in both peripheral and central pain models. In contrast, the n-hexane and butanolic extracts did

Antidiabetic activity

Azari Z., et al. (2018) A research study looked into how *Viola odorata* hydro-alcoholic and aqueous extracts affected the biochemical indicators and liver histology of adult Wistar rats with diabetes. The results showed that all tested dosages (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg) of the hydro-alcoholic extract, as well as a 400 mg/kg dose of the aqueous extract, substantially lowered blood glucose levels in diabetic rats. Additionally, by lowering inflammation, congestion, and increasing cell count, the aqueous extract at 100 and 400 mg/kg dosages enhanced the health of liver tissue. Additionally, these extracts significantly reduced the levels of the AST and ALT enzymes, suggesting possible liver-protective benefits.⁴¹

Antiasthmatic activity

Sardari M et.al (2015) The effectiveness of violet syrup in reducing coughing in children with intermittent asthma (ages 2–12) was investigated in a randomized controlled experiment. Compared to a placebo, the combination of violet syrup and short-acting beta-agonists significantly reduced coughing more quickly ($P = 0.001$, $P < 0.001$) in the 182 individuals in the research. Although younger children reacted better to the therapy, the data did not indicate any gender-based differences in efficacy. When combined with regular treatment, the researchers found that violet syrup significantly improves cough alleviation in children with intermittent asthma.

Toxicity

With the appropriate curative dosages, no adverse effects or dangers have been seen. The study examined the acute toxicity of *Viola odorata*

extract in rats by evaluating the toxicity of butanol, mg/kg. Within 24 hours of oral treatment of all methanol, and an aqueous extract of the aerial extracts, the treated rats exhibit normal activity, no portions of the plant at a maximum dosage of 2000 mortality rate, and destructive behavior.⁴²

Table No. Traditional uses of *Viola odorata*

Plant part	Specific diseases	Traditional uses
Plant	Antiinflammatory	Research suggests that <i>Viola odorata</i> aqueous extract may help treat lung inflammation due to its anti-inflammatory properties. ⁴³
Plant	Diabetis	The aqueous and hydroalcoholic extract of <i>viola osorata</i> improves the cell count, inflammation. ⁴⁴
Plant	Cancer	The study demonstrated that the extract effectively suppressed the progression of chemically induced tongue dysplasia, suggesting potential therapeutic benefits in preventing oral precancerous lesions. ⁴⁵
plant	Antioxidant	The crude methanolic extract used for the antioxidant potential ⁴⁶
Plant	Antipyretic	The extract of <i>Viola odorata</i> is used for its antipyretic effect
Leaves	Antihypertensive	The leaves extract used to lower blood pressure ⁴⁷
Leaves	Antidyslipidemic	The leaves extract used for the inhibition of lipid ⁴⁷
Plant	Reduce body weight	The study found that the plant extract demonstrated lipid-lowering effects by inhibiting both lipid synthesis and absorption, while also exhibiting significant antioxidant properties. ⁴⁸
Plant	Hepatoprotective	<i>Viola odorata</i> extract improves the liver tissue ⁴⁹
Bark	Antitubercular	Ethanolic extract of <i>viola odorata</i> used to treat tuberculosis. ⁵⁰
Plant	Depressant	Hydroalcoholic extract of <i>Viola odorata</i> is used to treat depression.
Aerial parts	Anti-bacterial	The methanolic extract of the plant is used to treat the bacteria.
Plant	Repellant activity	The plant extract used to treat the repellent activity. ⁵¹
Flower	Antifungal	The plant extract of <i>viola odorata</i> was used to treat the antifungal activity against <i>C. albicans</i> . ^{52,53}
Plant	Laxative	According to the study, a water-based extract of <i>Viola odorata</i> showed promise as a natural laxative agent by significantly softening stool and increasing bowel movements in mouse models.
Flowers	Migraine	When compared to placebo treatment, clinical trials showed that <i>Viola odorata</i> extract dramatically reduced migraine symptoms, indicating that it may be a viable alternative therapy option for migraine management.
Plant	Asthma	In children with intermittent asthma, the <i>Viola odorata</i> extract significantly reduced coughing and was more effective than conventional therapies. ⁵⁴

DISCUSSION

Viola odorata has revealed a wide range of pharmacological activities that support its traditional uses in various medicinal systems, its

rich phytochemical content, especially flavonoids, alkaloids & saponins. its an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial & hepatoprotective. Studies confirm its effectiveness in treating conditions such as respiratory infections, diabetes, liver damage, insomnia, & asthma. Also, its role in managing metabolic syndrome through antihypertensive, antidyslipidemic & weight-reducing effect has been authenticated. The plant also shows propitious neuroprotective & analgesic potential. Toxicity studies suggest it is safe at curative doses. Overall, viola odorata is an important medicinal herb, but further clinical research & ethical culture are needed to support its continued uses and development in current medicine

CONCLUSION

Viola odorata is a medicinally significant plant with a long history of use in traditional medicine systems, promoted by modern pharmacological validation, it various therapeutic effects, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, antidiabetic, and neuroprotective activities are attributed to its rich phytochemical profile. Clinical & experimental studies highlight its possible in treating respiratory ailment metabolic disorders, liver diseases & neurological conditions; importantly, toxicity studies confirm its safety at felicitous doses. Continue research, clinical authorisation & supportable culture are essential to fully harness its medicinal potential and ensure its accessibility for further therapeutic use.

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